

ISic3031

I.Sicily inscription 3031

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra riolitica locale)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

necropolis

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 12336

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μάτερις

2. ὁ Πεισάνδρο

Apparatus

Meligunìs Lipára XII

Translation (en)

Materis, son of Peisandros

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645387

PHI 334106

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3031. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357090>